

Reading Culture and the Use of the Library Among the Nigerian Youths

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Abstract

Reading, especially in this digital age where most people can attempt to read or write, should be a lifestyle. It goes beyond academic performance, as the benefits of one who reads include being empathetic, open to people, and understanding divergent points of view, hence the ability to integrate. Libraries are essential for learning and developing via information and knowledge, and so their availability and accessibility are key to promoting a reading culture for a developed and informed society. This paper examines reading culture among the youth and the use of the library. The study adopted a qualitative and descriptive method of investigation. The study discovered that while a handful of youth do not read due to the unavailability of library structures by the government and schools, if available and equipped, they could take up a healthy reading culture with all its benefits. This work concluded that the benefits of reading culture for individuals and society at large must not be compromised for a better functioning society. Hence, amidst other recommendations, the availability of well-functioning libraries in every local government area by the federal, state, and now local government was highly recommended.

Keywords: Reading, reading culture, library, youth.

INTRODUCTION

Reading goes beyond class, race, age, and gender as it can be likened to a free magic carpet ride to anywhere. Every child deserves to have access to a love of literature and is not only able to decode, segment, and blend with ease, but they also have a genuine adoration for the power of prose. In order to establish a lasting relationship with reading, we must build a strong reading culture in schools. A reading culture is an environment where reading is championed, valued, respected, and encouraged. Reading is of utmost importance to a child's personal, social, and academic success and their general well-being (Hawthorne A., 2021)

Reading yet transcends improving students' literary skills and overall academic performance; people who read are more empathetic towards people, more curious, and open to people who are different from themselves, which is integration. It also increases our understanding of our own

identity, improves empathy, and provides insight into our worldview of others. Reading used to mean sitting down with a book and turning pages as a story unfolded, but nowadays, it is rather sitting down with a device (Shaikh, n.d.).

Research studies have shown that there is a significant relationship between reading, learning, and intelligence, as the analytical skills that provide the ability to comprehend issues and resolve difficulties are the result of extensive reading. Reading regularly improves mental health as it provides a therapeutic impact and inner tranquility, while slowing down mental decline. Therefore, the relationship between reading empowerment is critical for economic and societal development.

The term "youth" refers to individuals who fall within the age range of 15 to 30 years old, with some variations depending on the individual, country, and definition of youth. For example, the legal definition of youth in Japan is up to 42 years old (Asodi, A), but the African Youths

Cheater defines youths as people between the ages of 15 and 35. Thus, since middle age starts at that age, developmental theorist Erik Erikson's theory of development takes that age into consideration for this work (Kasumba, G. 2023).

According to Rangathan (2014), a library is a public institution or establishment charged with the care of books, the duty of making them accessible to those who require their use. This means libraries are essential for learning and development via reading, of course.

Reading is a means for language acquisition, communication, and sharing information and ideas. It requires continuous practical development and critical analysis. Reading culture is, therefore, a foundational skill for learning and academic achievement, and with worldwide concerns with literacy rates, many countries have come to recognize the importance of reading instruction and strategies.

Every youth is expected to grow mentally, emotionally, and psychologically, and reading is one of the most important ways to achieve that within the knowledge of the world around us. Every book read grants an opportunity to learn new things and explore new ideas, increases one's knowledge, and makes one smarter.

Reading

In the earlier days, reading was habitual even for those who were not as educated as to go to school, but could read and probably write. Winter, C. (2003) noted that prior to the electronic era, everyday reading was a ritual that almost everyone who wanted knowledge conformed to. There was no need to remind of the need to read. Amidst so much going on, we have been so preoccupied with social media and the internet that hardly anyone contemplates reading a book, especially among the youth of today. While some may be so busy that they cannot read, others just don't care to read. And this is most deplorable in our society today.

Reading is the process of looking at a series of written symbols with meaning, and when we read, our eyes receive written symbols (letters, punctuation marks, and spaces) and our brain converts them into words, sentences, and

paragraphs that communicate something meaningful to us. It is a receptive skill through which we receive information (English CLUB, n.d.).

Reading is a process with various stages (before, during, and after reading) at which different tasks need to be performed. Reading is interactive, as the mind of the readers interacts, conducts a dialogue, actively engages with the text to decode, assign meaning, and interpret (SEA, n.d). Although reading may appear to be, one will be thankful in the long run. Here are some of the importance of reading by the University of the People.

Reading is of great value as it provides the means by which you get to:

- **Strengthens Brain Activity:** This mind gets working as it involves comprehensive processing in order to process the words you read. It is a neurobiological activity that works out the brain muscles and thereby, lowers the risks of Alzheimer.
- **Boost Communication skills:** to become better at writing and learning new words, it is necessary to read more to improve one's communication skills.
- **Help self-exploration:** one thing reading does is to expose one to thinking things in new ways, open to learn about cultures, events and ways that help to enhance one's identity.
- **Makes one intellectually sound:** when someone is said to be "well read" the more one reads as knowledge is power. This enables one to make and engage in sound conversations.
- **Entertains:** since reading has the capacity to keep one engaged, that is the ability to entertain.
- **Impacts good values:** it teaches the difference between right and wrong and explores various cultural views as well.
- **Enhances creativity:** Reading certainly boost ones level of creativity and expressions as it brings to life one's wildest imaginations.
- **Lowers stress:** Reading is therapeutic as it has been proven that it lowers stress by increasing relaxation via meditative abilities.

Summarizingly, reading is good, because it improves ones' focus, memory, empathy and communication skills. It de-stresses, improves ones' mental health and help one live longer. It allows one to learn new things, to aid one to succeed in work and relationships. One stands the chance to gain all of these benefits and some fantastic entertainment by reading books (Law, T.J., 2023).

Library

The word library comes from the latin word *liber*, meaning “book”. In Greek and Roman language, the corresponding term is *bibliotheca*. A collection or group of collection of books and or other print or nonprint materials organized and maintained for use such as reading, consultation, study and research etc (Libguides, American Library Association, 2022).

In similar definition, library is collection of information resources in prints or in other forms that is organized and made accessible for reading or study. It is important to note that the library makes knowledge accessible as availability does not necessarily means accessibility. By accessibility, we mean reachable, in use that's why it collects information for use

According to Etebu (2021), a library is a place where information materials (books, and non-book or print and non-print) are acquired, processed, organised and made available to library users for education, research, recreation and leisure. It is also a building or room containing collections of books, periodicals, and sometimes films recorded music for use or borrowing by the public or the member of an institution (Oxford Languages, n.d.).

A library may differ in size, may be organized for the use and maintained by a public body such as a government, an institution such as a school or museum; a corporation; or a private individual. In addition to providing materials, it provides the services of librarians who are trained and experts at finding, selecting, circulating and organizing information and interpreting information needs, navigating and analyzing very large amounts of information with a variety of resources. Libraries are mostly quiet areas for studying, as well as common

areas for group study, and collaboration, and may provide public facilities for access to their electronic resources such as computers and access to the internet for free or a very little token fee (Library-Wikipedia).

In a quick review, the purpose and objective of a library is to serve the society via the record of human thoughts, ideas and expressions by making them available to all with different kind of books and other reading materials at one place; to preserve literature for posterity; and to provide for study and research (Blisc, 2016).

There cannot be enough emphasis concerning the need of a library and the use of a library especially in these days of declining approach in the use of library. Hence, the two major reasons for the decline of reading Culture in Nigeria includes, the lack of institutions and artifacts that ensures such cultural perspectives and the deterioration of socio-economic welfare of the society (Chukwudera, n.d.).

Problem Statement

The reading culture in Nigeria has taken quite a sharp decline as so many youths today know too little or nothing about reading and its benefits to themselves and to the society at large. Our society is quite unhealthy and this is a consequence largely due to the fact that children and youth do not read. Institutions of learning such as schools has contributed immensely to the deteriorating reading culture as reading is not a concern anymore from the primary schools up to the tertiary institutions. Libraries are central to promoting reading culture, but are met with lack of required attention, from non existence of libraries to sparsely existing ones and situated away from urban and rural areas, to poor funding by the government and the bodies responsible. Hence, the detail of this study is to unravel the youth and the reading culture and the use of library in our society today with a view of highlighting the needed attention to bringing back focus to reading and proffer solutions to the lack of use of libraries for a healthier society.

Methodology

The data for this study was collected from secondary sources. Secondary data services include the internet, research articles,

newspapers and publications were broadly analyzed as a qualitative descriptive method of inquiry. This study considered the youth between the age is to 40 years with the purpose to figure out how the youth can return to culture and the use of library for a better and healthier society.

Reading Culture in Nigeria

Africa has been labelled a continent over the last decade, with a huge decline in the reading culture. This is quite evident that the passion for extracurricular reading and the spot to satisfy the curiosities that lead to reading are on the decline, just like the quality of life, and so buying books by the average working class is proving quite expensive. It is enough to ask why the reading culture in Nigeria is deteriorating at such a rate (Chukwudera, n.d.). He opines further that, like every other culture, the reading culture is not dependent, but associated to a whole lot of distinct factors either with or without are responsible, and as you know, cultural growth is to a large extent dependent on consciousness. The incline to read comes natural to man as it makes up one entire existence; from reading people, to reading weather, to reading the moods of people, and also reading meaning to our day to day conversations e. t. c. all of these are driven by curiosity and this insights compulsion.

According to Afikpo (2022), it's a saying that, if you want to hide something from an African, you put it in a book. This idea was further endorsed when the World Culture Score Index ranked Nigeria as one of the lowest reading culture countries in the world. Only two African countries made it to the list of countries that read, that is South Africa and Egypt.

As painful as this may be or even sound, this detrimental development is a huge threat to the our country Nigeria, as our nation has not given the required attention to the contending reading culture. Learning can only be achieved via reading and a nation such as ours famous for such literacy history is gradually been erased. A nation once known for parading the best set of authors and publishers in the whole of Africa. It was a time when there was a passion for reading for both the old and the young and even those with little education. This reading tendency did reflect on the quality of leadership and civil

discipline which made Nigeria stand tall among its counterparts in Africa especially. The reading culture in Nigeria suffered from widespread poverty, corruption, ineptitude and the death of dedicated quiet reading spaces like libraries. The degenerated standard of education has terribly altered reading ability among Nigerians as the effect is visible in our society by the inability of Nigerian youths to cope with distractions and the challenges that come with being adults. Possibly for socio-economic reasons such as the high cost of books, has led to the low turnout of readers, it is noteworthy that there is a beneficial relationship between reading and intelligence. The ability to analyze situations provides the ability to understand given situations and proffer solutions are the result of intensive reading. Reading liability giver rise to improve mental health which in turn improves ones empathy, social skills, healthy balanced relationships, it is therapeutic and slows down mental decline. Therefore, the relationship between reading, knowledge acquisition, intelligence and personal empowerment is crucial for economic and societal development. This critical mode of thinking and human development is lost in the absence of reading (MACK IV CONSULT, n.d.)

With the current situation of our nations' economy and the state of insecurity, one can be and should be very unstable. But, there are tools, very ready tools such as reading, be it newspapers, novels, books of interest for children and young and old adults to enable us make a lead way in whatever situation we find ourselves. The youths of today feels that money solves all problems, that is the quantitative aspect of life which does not amount to much asides show offs! But, reading and concentrating produces a qualitative life which has the ability to create and recreate a better society at large.

Available statistics from National Communication for Mass Literacy, Adults and Non-Formal Education has shown that 38 % of Nigerians are non literate as 4 in 10 primary school children cannot read for comprehension (MARK IV CONSULT, n.d). Shaikh, n.d., noted that, research aid data from common sense media found out disturbing trends in children reading habit and abilities in recent decades; 32% of children within the ages 15 to

17 read no books during the summer compared with 22% in 2016, while that of ages 9 to 11 who do not read doubled from 7% to 14%. This believes the question how do we stop this trend?

Hawthorne., 2021 opined that, creating a reading culture should not be the responsibility of an individual alone but, of dedicated senior leadership team, and advocated senior leadership team, and advocated by every pupil, parent, career and staff member in the school community as this requires dedication, perseverance and a lot of effort. Building a strong reading culture positions reading at the forefront of school improvement, from primary to the tertiary. This is because, a creative and exciting reading culture not only breeds capable and committed readers, but for wellbeing, community connectedness and student outcomes.

The State of Nigerian Libraries and its Importance

Even in the digital era, there is no substitute for books because they are the most essential component of education and play a crucial role in educating us. A library is a structure or space where various types of books are gathered for the purpose of reading. Online information can be obtained using PCs, which include laptops, palmtops, and phones. This is an additional tool for using academic libraries. Donors are no longer dependent on academic libraries as a vital component of education and research. Since libraries are recognized as sources of information for today's information seekers, it is important to make sure that academic libraries lead the way in terms of information creation, distribution, and provision (Iresearching, n.d.).

The library is one of the most conducive places to read conveniently besides the availability of books and other resources. It is a place to meet other people with minds and perspective which is a whole lot. Although some persons find it difficult to make a head way in using the library, as lightly observed by Maliwasane and Mudzielwana (2016), that, students are faced with challenges such as lack of knowledge on the use of information retrieval tools, insufficient users education, lack of computer knowledge and lack of information technology (ICT) in accessing information. Although, this

is why libraries consist of library staff to direct and aid in searching for information in the libraries.

In Nigeria, libraries are severely neglected, and this problem affects state, public, school, and other levels of government. The Federal Capital Territory (FCT), state library boards in each of the 36 states, and the FCT educational secretariat are all part of the National Library of Nigeria (NLN), which operates 34 state branches nationwide. While some states do not have the same level of financing for their libraries, many state libraries see variable results from their funding source. Nigeria's 774 local government area councils are meant to each have a public library, but sadly, some states only have one library in the state capital, depriving their inhabitants of this opportunity.

that is not so as some states only have one library in the state capital, thereby denying its citizens access to such facilities. The fact that public libraries have over the years experienced poor funding is quite glaring in some states today. This is obvious that, the library facility is not priority to these leaders who are supposed to be promoting advancement for its people. These problems range between lack of purchase of new/modern information resources over a long period of time, to dilapidated, inconclusive structures, to poor regulation, incentive and irregular salaries for public libraries and so led to a drastic shortage of staff. Some of the public libraries are yet to become ICT complaint (e-libraries, internet) and so analogue. The professional development opportunities for state public librarians are low or not at all in existence as there are very low or not at all in existence in most states (Okeagu, 2022).

If knowledge is power, then the access to knowledge is almost not in existence as there are very few library facilities and many citizens especially the children and the youths cannot access these. And this can be tagged to lack of development.

Libraries are very important today as they play a crucial role in promoting education, knowledge and community. Here are some importance of library by Enlightio (2022):

- Libraries provide access to a wealth of information and knowledge anyone can

learn, discover and develop not minding the age, education, or ones' income. Accessible to everyone include non-fiction to children books, online data bases, e-books

- Audio books and amidst other digital resources. Available also are research materials, reference guides, educational resources, programs and events such as books clubs, workshops, lectures for learning and interactions with other people, and so on.
- With the space provision in libraries for discussions, comes a sense of community, where people can relate and socialize with people and engage in meaningful discussion and arguments as this enables growth and keep them well informed and engaged.
- Libraries have books available and stored and has provision for borrowing books for free or a token and this enables readers enjoy a wide selection of reading materials at little or no cost. Libraries therefore, help save money. Digital materials can also be downloaded to e-readers or other devices via access to computers and internet services.
- Libraries is a facility that can preserve history as it also functions by collecting and storing materials like books, documents, photographs, video recordings, providing researchers and historians with lots of information an understanding and connection of the past and how it has shaped out today. Libraries do not have the techniques for carefully cataloging and preserving these materials and protect them from deteriorating for future generations.
- Libraries are incredibly useful in out would today as they inspire creativity and imagination. Story books, novels and other resources magnify imaginations. Young minds feel safe to explore new concepts by engaging contents of knowledge from science and technology to history and culture.
- Libraries also author's democracy as it equips with motion and socio- economic trends in the country and in comparison with other nations of the free expression and analytical dialoguer.
- Libraries are lastly, incredibly functional and of great value to the educational system anywhere and at any level of educational

attainment as it provides a wide range of information, resources, and services. It is a safe zone for studies to read, study, learn and search for new ideas. Students can access information for projects, research paper and assignments. There are quantum of resources and programs accessible for students learning and development, and not to mention skilled staff for navigating the library facilities.

The importance of library usage cannot be overemphasized as this books a reading culture for propagating great minds in the society for national advancement. There is a saying that goes thus; tomorrow is in the hands of the today's' youth "let us channel the youth to exploring their great minds and creativity for a better and stable tomorrow, we owe them that much. A dormant field they say yields noting and so the youth is without reading culture. How then do not restore cultivate and foster a reading culture in our deteriorating society today? Hence, the following recommendations.

Conclusion

There is certainly no doublet that a healthy reading culture form our findings is of economics benefit to any society from a personal/individuals perspective such as, stable emotions,

improved mental health, personal development in terms of self-exploration, improved communication skills and enhanced creativity. All of these translate into a healthy society with vibrant youths with a high sense of ideals /principles which positions a nation on a path to steady lasting development.

This is attainable when the youth are exposed to reading and using the libraries as this curbs crime and propels quality innovative ideas among them.

The use of Libraries and its relevance cannot be overemphasized, for its conducive environment for reading and research, and quality dialogue which can result in advancing critical and innovative thinking and this is crucial for socio-economic development. However, the likening of Africans as a people who do not read only proves that the lack of enthusiasm towards

reading especially among the youth today is due to the degenerating state of the libraries facilities, hence a poor reading culture.

It is noteworthy that, Nigerians in Diaspora are regarded as the most educated people in most counties and are doing innovatively excellently well. This is due to the conducive and well functioning library facilities they have at their disposal and have impressed reading culture. On this proposition, therefore, better than before if more libraries are built and existing ones revamped. The youths so pregnant will deliver innovative ideas if given the chance.

Recommendations

The prize to pay for nation that does not read can likened to a sinking ship and as a country ranked among the lowest in the world with regards to reading culture, hence these selected commendations for restoring a reading culture and library use among the youth in days society.

Firstly, library services should be extended to the urban and local areas for feasibility as most libraries are located in the cities of Nigeria. As a matter of policy, the Government can achieve this by mandating that every local government area has its own libraries and a functioning one at that.

Secondly, due to inadequate funding, many library facilities are in dilapidated states with no books or outdated books, no internet services and so on. Funding should be made available by the government for up- dating library materials and structures for smooth functioning of existing libraries.

Thirdly, reading culture should be promoted from the primary school level by ensuring the use of library, schools owning their libraries or co-owning libraries and also them in order to fascinate them and ensure an early state of reading culture.

Lastly, reading culture should be promoted at home with parents reading and or encouraging the children to read books by buying books and also creating reading space at the home. This will further engrain in them the habit of reading and loving it.

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